

A European network of Trusted Research Environments to support sensitive data management

This policy brief outlines the importance of European investment in Trusted Research Environment services and offers five recommendations for funders, policymakers and national research infrastructure planners.

Summary

EOSC-ENTRUST's vision is a network of interoperable Trusted Research Environments (TREs) capable of supporting large-scale European research and analysis efforts on sensitive and restricted data¹.

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) are secure computer environments designed to handle sensitive data safely, digital reference libraries where researchers visit and analyse data in controlled environments, but cannot take the data away; only approved summaries may ever be exported. TREs come in various shapes and sizes, including **secure processing environments**, **secure data environments** and **data safe havens**, but their general purpose is to enable researchers to access sensitive datasets across borders whilst maintaining proper control of the data.

Increasing digitalisation across Europe is bringing new opportunities for more innovation and better use of data in policy-relevant research and analysis. Sensitive data, such as healthcare records, genomic data and clinical trial data, is tremendously valuable for researchers and policymakers, but access must be balanced with data privacy rights. Europe has shown the world how this can be regulated with the gold standard for data privacy, the GDPR. With such a clear, common foundation, Europe is uniquely placed to take the next steps in innovating cross-border research using sensitive data.

Innovation is particularly driven by linking datasets from multiple sources across national boundaries, to understand, for example, individuals' health and socio-economic status as they move between counties, the habitats of vulnerable species, geo-spatial locations

of sensitive sites and sampling of potential pathogen outbreaks. Linkage increases the value of data enormously, but also increases their sensitivity. To use linked data in research in a trustworthy way we need systems and processes that are safe, secure and transparent.

The growing adoption of TREs marks a significant advancement in secure research practices across Europe. However, without a coordinated approach, there is a risk of creating isolated, secure data silos that fragment the European research landscape. To address this, the EOSC-ENTRUST project is building a comprehensive blueprint for TREs, identifying gaps between the current needs and existing best practices capabilities of TREs, to support federation and interoperability. Analyses of current needs and existing best practices lead us to five initial recommendations:

1. Invest in TRE infrastructure, including hardware, software and people.
2. Promote TRE interoperability, to create the necessary ecosystem for data linkage.
3. Build on international standards and best practices, rather than start from scratch.
4. Nurture TRE communities, developing the human capital and cooperation required.
5. Build and maintain effective public engagement, maintaining our social licence for research with public data.

Recommendation 1

 Invest in TRE infrastructure

The European Commission and member states should invest in hardware, cloud computing, storage, backup systems, software solutions and service staff for national and regional TREs, to enhance their security, data storage and analytics capabilities. The trend away from data download and towards data access, or “data visiting”, for research with sensitive data is to be welcomed, and support for this safer, more trustworthy model requires investment in suitable facilities.

Recommendation 2

 Promote TRE interoperability

Alongside investment in TREs must come the adoption of interoperability standards. To realise the benefits of research and innovation we must be able to combine and link data between TREs. This will require not only technical standards for network security and data exchange, but also organisational and governance models to agree and manage the standards, processes and accreditations needed to build and maintain the network of trust between TREs.

The EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint² is laying the foundation for this interoperable network.

A driver use-case: cross-border clinical trials

The sharing and reusing of clinical research data is increasingly regarded as vital for accelerating scientific discoveries and improving healthcare provision. Pooling data from multiple studies in meta-analyses and systematic reviews increases statistical power and enhances confidence in results. Linking study data to routinely collected health data brings fuller understanding, richer insights, greater efficiency and increased safety. Despite a call to action from major stakeholders, the percentage of clinical research studies that make their data available for reuse remains low. Reasons cited include ethical, legal, organisational, semantic and technical barriers – barriers that a secured network of TREs will help overcome.

Recommendation 3

 Build on international standards and best practices

The new TRE infrastructure does not need to start from scratch. We can, and should, build on international best practices, from the Five Safes research principles³ and the SATRE standard architecture for TREs⁴ through to Europe’s detailed design thinking around data spaces⁵. Standards like these form the foundations of the EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint for TREs.

The Five Safes

The Five Safes principles for enabling research with sensitive data have become a common way for TREs to think about the needs and tradeoffs in managing safe research. They are usually framed as five questions:

- **Safe people:** Can the users be trusted to use the data appropriately?
- **Safe projects:** Is this use of the data appropriate, lawful, ethical and sensible?
- **Safe settings:** Does the access facility limit unauthorised use or mistakes?
- **Safe data:** Does the data itself contain sufficient information to allow confidentiality to be breached?
- **Safe outputs:** Is confidentiality maintained for the outputs of the management regime?

Recommendation 4

Nurture TRE communities

We must foster a collaborative TRE ecosystem by funding working groups, organising events and creating forums to enable knowledge sharing among service providers, data custodians, researchers and the public. These new ways of working should be supported by developing training materials, recognising new roles and career paths and building the necessary incentives into research culture. In promoting TRE interoperability we must also take care to standardise what is necessary but not to over-prescribe and inadvertently strangle innovation. Our goal must be a thriving and diverse community of users, suppliers and innovators.

The EOSC-ENTRUST Training Package⁶ is gathering and signposting community training resources.

RDA Working Group on TREs

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) is a global grass-roots initiative whose goal is to improve data sharing across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address the grand challenges of society⁷.

Building on meetings in 2023 in Gothenburg and Salzburg, European researchers and TRE operators are leading the way on establishing the first global working group on TRE standards.

Recommendation 5

Build and maintain effective public engagement

When we enable research using public data, the data subjects, the European public, must remain centre stage. Public involvement and engagement with research using sensitive data should be inclusive, from design through to recruitment and reporting. National public engagement specialists should be involved in the creation and dissemination of clear and engaging content in local languages, with particular attention given to hard to reach groups. Wherever feasible, the public should be genuine partners in all stages of the research – on focus groups, advisory boards and research approval panels – with their opinions and concerns feeding into decision making at the highest levels.

Conclusion

Europe's adoption of a common regulatory environment for personal data – GDPR – creates a legal foundation for research at scale with sensitive data unprecedented anywhere else. The potential this offers can only be realised if Europe has the systems and processes in place to protect and safeguard these data and its citizens' privacy.

Trusted research environments across Europe have demonstrated their abilities to provide such safeguards, each in their own ways, driven by the immediate needs of their users. It is timely to ask the question: how best can we connect these systems in safe, secure and standard ways to stimulate the sharing of, and access to, sensitive and confidential data to accelerate scientific discoveries.

EOSC-ENTRUST has risen to this challenge and recommends that policymakers and funders embrace the TRE model and help promote it through investment, advocacy and public engagement.

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